

L-MOMENTS FOR PEARSON TYPE VII DISTRIBUTION

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ABSTRACT. In this article, we introduce the differential equation formulated by Carl Pearson that leads to the derivation of the Pearson type VII probability density function. We then apply numerical methods to calculate the L-moments of this distribution.

1. INTRODUCTION

Between 1890 and 1895, Carl Pearson devised a system by which a differential equation of the following form applies to each probability density function,

$$\frac{1}{p} \frac{dp}{dx} = -\frac{a+x}{C_0 + C_1x + C_2x^2}. \quad (1.1)$$

The shape of the distribution depends on the values of parameters a, C_0, C_1 , and C_2 . Pearson classified different shapes into several types. The solution form of relation (1.1) depends on the nature of the roots of the following equation,

$$C_0 + C_1x + C_2x^2 = 0.$$

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The Pearson type VII distribution corresponds to this state that: $C_0 > 0, C_1 = a = 0, C_2 > 0$, in this case,

$$\frac{d \log P(x)}{dx} = -\frac{x}{C_0 + C_2 x^2}.$$

Therefore, we have

$$P(x) = K(C_0 + C_2 x^2)^{-(2C_2)^{-1}}.$$

Also, we can show [1] this probability density function has the following form,

$$P(x) = \frac{1}{\alpha \beta(m - \frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2})} \left[1 + \left(\frac{x - \lambda}{\alpha} \right)^2 \right]^{-m}.$$

Students t-distribution is a special case [3] of Pearson type VII distribution with $\lambda = \mu, \alpha = \sqrt{V\sigma^2}$ and $m = \frac{V+1}{2}$, $P(x|\mu, \sigma^2, V) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{V\sigma^2} \beta(\frac{V}{2}, \frac{1}{2})} (1 + \frac{1}{V} (\frac{x-\mu}{\alpha})^2)^{-\frac{V+1}{2}}$.

2. L-MOMENTS

Certain linear combinations of order statistics of a random sample contain information about the location, dispersion, and shape of the distribution [2]. Denote by $X_{K:n}$, the K^{th} smallest observation from a sample of size n , so that the ordered sample is $X_{1:n} \leq X_{2:n} \leq \dots \leq X_{n:n}$. The L-moments of a probability distribution are defined by

$$\lambda_1 = E(X_{1:1}), \quad \lambda_2 = \frac{1}{2}E(X_{2:2} - X_{1:2}), \quad \lambda_3 = \frac{1}{3}E(X_{3:3} - 2X_{2:3} + X_{1:3}).$$

3. MAIN THEOREM

In this section, we present a theorem in which the L-moments for Pearson type VII distribution are estimated.

Theorem 3.1. *L-moments for Pearson type VII distribution satisfy*

$$\lambda_1 = \lambda, \quad \lambda_2 \simeq \theta^2 \sum_{k=0}^3 w_k \mathcal{F}(x_k) - \lambda,$$

$$\lambda_3 \simeq \eta^3 \left(\sum_{k=0}^3 w_k (\mathcal{G}(x_k) + \mathcal{F}(x_k) + 4\mathcal{H}(x_k)) \right) - 4\eta^2 \sum_{k=0}^3 w_k \mathcal{F}(x_k).$$

In the proof, we introduce $\mathcal{F}(x), \mathcal{G}(x), \mathcal{H}(x), w_k, x_k, \theta$, and η .

Proof. In this proof, w_k denotes the k^{th} weight, and x_k represents the k^{th} point in Gaussian quadrature. By performing two changes of variables, we can transform the integral below into an appropriate form for numerical 4-point Gaussian integration. So, we first let $u = e^t$ and then let $v = \frac{2u}{e^x} - 1$;

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{-\infty}^x \left[1 + \left(\frac{t - \lambda}{\alpha} \right)^2 \right]^{-m} dt &= \int_0^{e^x} \left[1 + \left(\frac{\ln(u) - \lambda}{\alpha} \right)^2 \right]^{-m} u^{-1} du \\ &= \int_{-1}^1 f(v) dv \simeq h(x) := \sum_{k=0}^3 w_k f(x_k), \end{aligned} \quad (3.1)$$

where $f(v) = [1 + (\frac{x + \ln(v+1) - \ln(2) - \lambda}{\alpha})^2]^{-m} (v+1)^{-1}$ and we previously determined the values of m, α and λ . So, by using (3.1) and changing the variable to $u = \frac{2}{\pi} \tan^{-1}(x)$, the following integral can be approximated as:

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} x \left[1 + \left(\frac{x - \lambda}{\alpha} \right)^2 \right]^{-m} \int_{-\infty}^x \left[1 + \left(\frac{t - \lambda}{\alpha} \right)^2 \right]^{-m} dt dx \\ \simeq \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} x \left[1 + \left(\frac{x - \lambda}{\alpha} \right)^2 \right]^{-m} h(x) dx = \int_{-1}^1 \mathcal{F}(u) du \simeq \sum_{k=0}^3 w_k \mathcal{F}(x_k), \end{aligned} \quad (3.2)$$

where $\mathcal{F}(u) = \tan(\frac{u\pi}{2}) [1 + (\frac{\tan(\frac{u\pi}{2}) - \lambda}{\alpha})^2]^{-m} h(\tan(\frac{u\pi}{2})) (1 + \tan^2(\frac{u\pi}{2})) (\frac{\pi}{2})$.

Similarly, if $\mathcal{H}(u) := \mathcal{F}(u) h(\tan(\frac{u\pi}{2}))$, we can demonstrate that

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} x \left[1 + \left(\frac{x - \lambda}{\alpha} \right)^2 \right]^{-m} \left\{ \int_{-\infty}^x \left[1 + \left(\frac{t - \lambda}{\alpha} \right)^2 \right]^{-m} dt \right\}^2 dx \\ \simeq \sum_{k=0}^3 w_k \mathcal{H}(x_k). \end{aligned} \quad (3.3)$$

The integral below can be estimated by transforming it into a convenient form through two changes of variables: first $u = e^{-t}$ and then

$v = 2ue^x - 1$. Hence,

$$\int_x^{+\infty} \left[1 + \left(\frac{t - \lambda}{\alpha} \right)^2 \right]^{-m} dt = \int_0^{e^{-x}} \left[1 + \left(\frac{\ln(u) + \lambda}{\alpha} \right)^2 \right]^{-m} u^{-1} du = \int_{-1}^1 g(v) dv \simeq k(x) := \sum_{k=0}^3 w_k g(x_k), \tag{3.4}$$

where $g(v) = [1 + (\frac{\ln(v+1) - \ln(2) - x + \lambda}{\alpha})^2]^{-m} (v + 1)^{-1}$. So, by using (3.4) and changing the variable to $u = \frac{\pi}{2} \tan^{-1}(x)$, we have

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} x \left[1 + \left(\frac{x - \lambda}{\alpha} \right)^2 \right]^{-m} \left\{ \int_x^{+\infty} \left[1 + \left(\frac{t - \lambda}{\alpha} \right)^2 \right]^{-m} dt \right\}^2 dx \simeq \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} x \left[1 + \left(\frac{x - \lambda}{\alpha} \right)^2 \right]^{-m} k^2(x) dx = \int_{-1}^1 \mathcal{G}(u) du \simeq \sum_{k=0}^3 w_k \mathcal{G}(x_k), \tag{3.5}$$

where $\mathcal{G}(u) = \tan(\frac{u\pi}{2}) [1 + (\frac{\tan(\frac{u\pi}{2}) - \lambda}{\alpha})^2]^{-m} g^2(\tan(\frac{u\pi}{2})) (1 + \tan^2(\frac{u\pi}{2})) (\frac{\pi}{2})$.

Let $\theta = \frac{1}{\alpha\beta(m-1, \frac{1}{2})}$, $\eta = \frac{1}{\alpha\beta(m-\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2})}$ and $\phi(x) = (1 + (\frac{x-\lambda}{\alpha})^2)^{-m}$, then we have

$$\lambda_1 = E(X) = \lambda, \quad \lambda_2 = \theta^2 \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} x \phi(x) \int_{-\infty}^x \phi(t) dt dx - \lambda, \\ \lambda_3 = \eta^3 \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} x \phi(x) \left(\int_x^{+\infty} \phi(t) dt \right)^2 dx + \eta^3 \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} x \phi(x) \int_{-\infty}^x \phi(t) dt dx - 4\eta^2 \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} x \phi(x) \int_{-\infty}^x \phi(t) dt dx + 4\eta^3 \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} x \phi(x) \left(\int_{-\infty}^x \phi(t) dt \right)^2 dx.$$

By substituting the values obtained from equations (3.2), (3.3), and (3.5) into the above equations, we can thoroughly validate our proof. \square

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